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Multifunctional Acidocin 4356 combats *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* through membrane perturbation and virulence attenuation: Experimental results confirmed molecular dynamic simulation

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Abstract

A longstanding awareness in generating resistance to common antimicrobial therapies by gram-negative bacteria has made them a major threat to global health. The application of antimicrobial peptides as a therapeutic agent would be a great opportunity to combat bacterial diseases. Here, we introduce a new antimicrobial peptide (~8.5 kDa) from probiotic strain *Lactobacillus acidophilus* ATCC 4356, designated as Acidocin 4356 (ACD). This multifunctional peptide exerts its anti-infective ability against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* through an inhibitory action on virulence factors, bacterial killing, and biofilm degradation. Reliable performance over tough physiological conditions and low hemolytic activity confirmed a new hope for the therapeutic setting. Antibacterial kinetic studies using flow cytometry technique showed that the ACD activity is related to the change in permeability of the membrane. The results obtained from molecular dynamic (MD) simulation were perfectly suited to the experimental data of ACD behavior. The structure-function relationship of this natural compound, along with the results of TEM analysis and molecular dynamic (MD) simulation, confirmed the ability of the ACD aimed at enhancing bacterial membrane perturbation. The peptide was effective in the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* infection in mouse model. The results support the therapeutic potential of ACD for the treatment of *Pseudomonas* infections.

Importance Multidrug-resistant bacteria are a major threat to global health, and *Pseudomonas* bacterium with the ability to form biofilms has considered as one of the main causative agents of nosocomial infections. Traditional antibiotics have failed because of increased resistance. So, finding new biocompatible antibacterial drugs are essential. Antimicrobial peptides are produced by various organisms as a natural defense mechanism against pathogens, inspiring for the possible design of the next generation of antibiotics. In this study, a new antimicrobial peptide was isolated from *Lactobacillus acidophilus* ATCC 4356, counteracting both biofilm and planktonic cells of *P. aeruginosa*. A detailed investigation was then conducted concerning the functional mechanism of this peptide by using fluorescence techniques, electron microscopy, and *in silico* methods. The antibacterial and antibiofilm properties of this peptide may be important in the treatment of *Pseudomonas* infections.